

We know there was a lot of information to take on board when starting on a hybrid closed loop system (HCL).

This leaflet provides a recap on how to keep yourself safe whilst using HCL, backup supplies, and emergency contact details for clinical or technical concerns.

Avoidance of Diabetic Ketoacidosis (DKA)

We are aware of a few instances across the country where people have been admitted to hospital with Diabetic Ketoacidosis (DKA) on HCL systems, these have been due to cannula failures, where glucose levels have been raised for a while but the user did not check for ketones or change their set, trusting that the system would sort it out.

Please remember it is very unusual for someone on HCL to have a glucose level over 13.0mmol/L for over 2hrs. If you continue to try and correct a high reading through the pump, it will only give you small correction doses because it has been trying to bring your sugars down and thinks there is more insulin on board but the cannula or infusion set are not working.

See sick days rules (overleaf)

How to avoid DKA

- Only give the pump one chance to get it right. If glucose levels have been above 13.0mmol/l for over 2 hrs despite auto-corrections from the pump
- Change cannula
- Manual injection via pen or syringe (usual correction ratio)
- Exit automode and run pump in manual mode for the insulin duration (3-4hrs)
- Check for ketones

If you do not have ketones please change your reservoir and cannula to be sure.

Cannula changes and timing

- These are clearly important in insulin pump therapy in general.
- With HCL systems, the importance is increased as any reduction in insulin absorption either due to poor sites or due to reduced infusion by keeping the cannula in longer may affect the total daily insulin dose and subsequent pump learning.
- Ensuring a full set change is completed every two to three days will minimise variability in absorption.

Travel checklist

When travelling, you need to consider bringing extra supplies with you.

- Details of holiday insurance if travelling abroad
- Letter on hospital-headed notepaper confirming diabetes, insulin pump and CGM use and the need to carry sharps.
- Emergency contact numbers for the insulin pump company and the hospital insulin pump team.
- Extra insulin and supplies of other medication.
- Adequate supplies for the pump, e.g. cannulas and lines.
- Long-acting insulin to use in the event of insulin pump failure.
- Insulin pens/needles or syringes.
- Spare pump (if available).
- Blood glucose meter, test strips, lancets and lancing device.
- Batteries for pump.
- Blood test strips to check for ketones.
- Hypo management supplies – dextrose tablets weigh less and are smaller than most liquids; also, they will not cause a problem in airport security.
- A method of safe sharps disposal.

Pump sick day rules (DAFNE UK) https://abcd.care/sites/abcd.care/files/BP_DTN_v13%20FINAL.pdf

Contact details

Clinical support

- Contact the diabetes nurses (Mon-Fri 9am-5pm) 0203 299 1353 or via email kch-tr.diabetesnurses@nhs.net.
- Outside of working hours for medical emergencies that cannot wait until the next working you can speak to the Diabetes Consultant via the hospital switchboard 0203 299 9000,.

Technical support by company

Medtronic

24hr helpline 01923 205 167
24hr online chatbot
<https://www.medtronic-diabetes.co.uk/contact>

CamDiab

Office hours only (Mon-Fri 9am-5pm)
Email: support@camdiab.com
Telephone **020 3695 3780**

Dexcom

Office hour only
Mon-Thu 9am-5.30pm
Fri 9am-4pm)

Advanced Therapeutics

Office hours (Mon-Fri 9am-5pm) 01926 833 273
Emergency out of hours helpline 07775 642 239

Air Liquide (Tandem T-Slim)

24hr helpline 0800 012 1560
Email: alhomecare.diabetes@nhs.net

0800 031 5761

DKA Toolkit:

Please ensure you have in date supplies and equipment for avoiding and managing DKA effectively:

- Blood ketone meter
- Blood ketone test strips (in date)
- Copy of pump sick day rules
- Rapid acting insulin in the form of a pen/syringe (In date)
- Long acting insulin in the form of a pen/syringe (in date)
- Conversion doses for going back to injections

• If you have ketones due to a cannula failure please exit automode and use sick day rules until the ketones have gone before going back into closed loop.

• Remember if you have needed to give a manual injection via pen or syringe do not go back into automode for the insulin duration (3-4hrs).